

Abstract

Potential Antiplatelet Activity of *Hypericum perforatum*.

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Abstract

Hypericum perforatum (HP) is currently one of the most widely consumed medicinal plants worldwide. Beyond its well-known use as an antidepressant, several studies have reported antibacterial, antioxidant, and antiviral properties of HP. Despite this therapeutic potential, many of the bioactivities attributed to HP still require further scientific validation. In Traditional Chinese Medicine, *Hypericum* (*Guan Ye Lian Qiao*) is classified as a heat-clearing herb and is commonly used to treat various infectious and inflammatory conditions. In contrast to the extensive literature on its antidepressant effects, little is known about the impact of HP on platelet function. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to investigate the potential relevance of HP in two key aspects of platelet physiology: platelet activation and platelet aggregation.

Methods: Platelet activation in the presence of HP extracts was characterised by flow cytometry through the assessment of molecular markers, including intracellular Ca^{2+} mobilisation and the expression of platelet activation receptors such as activated GPIIb/IIIa and P-selectin (CD62P). The effects of different concentrations of a total alcoholic extract of HP on platelet aggregation were evaluated in nine healthy donors using light transmission aggregometry with collagen as the agonist. Subsequently, dose–response curves were obtained from three independent experiments performed in a single individual, using collagen, adenosine diphosphate (ADP), and epinephrine as agonists.

Results: The results indicate a potential inhibitory effect of HP on platelet activation, which may be related to reduced intracellular calcium mobilisation and decreased expression of activated GPIIb/IIIa receptors. In addition, marked inter-individual variability was observed, along with a significant dose-dependent reduction in collagen-induced platelet aggregation in the presence of HP extracts (mean minimum inhibition of 8% at 0.068 mg es/mL and mean maximum inhibition of 43% at 0.456 mg es/mL). Based on these data, an IC_{50} value of 0.34 mg es/mL was determined.

Conclusions: Despite the inherent limitations of an in vitro study, these findings suggest that HP exerts a dose-dependent inhibitory effect on platelet function, affecting both activation and aggregation responses. Consequently, HP may be considered an herbal product with potential antiplatelet properties. Further studies are required to clarify its effects on haemostasis and to evaluate the clinical relevance of these findings.

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Effect of HP on the kinetics of free cytosolic Ca^{2+} after stimulation with thrombin (0.05 U/mL) in whole blood platelets. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM for three different experiments with the same donor. Fluorescence ratios = mean FL1 intensity in agonist-stimulated platelets / mean FL1 intensity in unstimulated platelets.

Effect of *Hypericum perforatum* on platelet aggregation induced by collagen (1 μ g/mL) in Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP).

Keywords: *Hypericum perforatum*; Flow Cytometry; Platelet Activation; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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